

Factors influencing the purchase intention of NEVs in emerging global markets

Athulathmudali Hirantha Sandun¹

¹School of Management, Shanghai University, CN

Abstract: Sustainable development and the promotion of sustainable energy have become crucial in the global community, with a focus on new energy vehicles (NEVs) as a key solution. This study aims to investigate the factors influencing the purchase intention of NEVs in emerging global markets. Drawing on the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Technology Acceptance Model, the study will explore factors such as environmental knowledge, NEV knowledge, external/social influence, attitude, policy support, and infrastructure maturity. Additionally, perceived value factors including financial value, environmental value, and social influence will be considered. The study seeks to understand how these factors interact to shape consumers' purchase intentions towards NEVs. By providing insights into consumer attitudes and intentions towards NEVs, this study aims to inform policymakers and industry stakeholders on effective strategies to promote sustainable transportation. The findings can contribute to the development of policies and incentives that support the adoption of NEVs in emerging global markets, ultimately advancing sustainable development goals.

Keywords: New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), Purchase Intention, Emerging Global Markets, Factors Influencing, Sustainable Development Goals, Theory of Planned Behavior, Technology Acceptance Model

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 25 September, 2024; **Published:** 26 September, 2024

How to cite this article: Athulathmudali Hirantha Sandun (2024). Factors influencing the purchase intention of NEVs in emerging global markets. *North American Academic Research*, 7(9), 54-68. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946843>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Background: The use of sustainable energy is important and an important step towards achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals 7 and 12 for 2030 (Wang et al., 2021). Sustainable development goals place a high priority on the production and use of green energy in various sectors (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022). Electric Vehicle (EV) and Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) integration is a hot topic due to the provided benefits on meeting the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Ahmed & Gomah, 2023).

However, there are increasing voices from segments of society calling for behavioral change towards more sustainable modes of transportation such as the use of electric vehicles (EVs), mobility sharing and rental services, and electric-powered public transportation (Arora et al., 2022). New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) have the potential to be an eco-friendly technology that can decrease the impact of automobiles on global warming and assist countries in reaching their goals outlined in the 2015 Paris Climate Agreement. As oil is a finite and depleting resource, it is necessary to replace it with alternative energy sources such as electricity to address transportation needs and support

future economic development. This shift will also enhance local air quality, reduce traffic noise, and create new business opportunities and preserve the natural environment for future generations through sustainable development (Arora et al., 2022).

New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) exert great potential in reducing carbon emissions, improving air quality and reducing the dependence on petroleum products (Wang et al., 2021). For the past decade, one of the most sustainable markets has been the electric vehicle (EVs) market. Giant automotive companies such as BMW, Mercedes, Volvo, Tesla, and Volkswagen have also entered the electric vehicle (EV) market. (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022).

The global community is increasingly recognizing the importance of sustainable development and the promotion of sustainable energy sources to address environmental challenges and reduce carbon emissions. In this context, new energy vehicles (NEVs) have emerged as a key solution to promote sustainable transportation and reduce reliance on traditional fossil fuel-powered vehicles. Understanding the factors influencing consumers' purchase intentions towards NEVs is essential for policymakers and industry stakeholders to develop effective strategies to promote their adoption in emerging global markets.

Objectives and Significance of the Study

Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the factors influencing consumers' purchase intentions of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) in emerging global markets, with a focus on the emerging global markets. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. Examine the impact of environmental knowledge, NEV knowledge, external/social influence, attitude, policy support, and infrastructure maturity on consumers' purchase intentions of NEVs.
2. Explore the perceived value factors, including financial value, environmental value, and social influence, in shaping consumers' attitudes towards NEVs.
3. Investigate how the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Technology Acceptance Model can be applied to understand consumers' intentions to purchase NEVs in emerging global markets.
4. Provide valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders to develop effective policies and incentives that support the adoption of NEVs in emerging global markets.
5. Contribute to the advancement of sustainable development goals by promoting the adoption of NEVs as a sustainable transportation option in emerging global markets.

By achieving these objectives, this study aims to fill the gap in the literature regarding green purchasing behavior towards NEVs in emerging global markets and provide practical recommendations for promoting the adoption of environmentally friendly vehicles in these regions.

Significance of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine and analyze factors influencing consumers' purchase intentions of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) in emerging global markets. As a result of globalization and with modern new media, we have strong connections with neighboring countries and share many common values without boundaries. The population in emerging global markets like South Asia is significantly higher, and the people in this region share a strong affinity for common interests. Especially, regional countries are very interested to see the developments and changes that have occurred in others. Still, emerging global markets like South Asian regional countries predominantly rely on traditional, conventional oil-based vehicles.

As emerging global markets' countries, they can set a positive example by adopting sustainable energy for transportation. By utilizing sustainable energy vehicles, they can leave a lasting impression on the global market and potentially become a catalyst for change in the Vehicle Market. There are large vehicle manufacturing companies

based in India, such as TATA and Mahindra, which export many vehicles to the South Asian region. However, the large quantities of exported vehicles still rely on traditional fossil fuels. The demand for new energy vehicles, such as electric vehicles, has yet to be determined through studies. Previous scholars have noted that there have been numerous attempts to analyze green purchasing behavior in Western countries, while there have been minimal studies conducted in developing countries (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021).

In this study, we are considering many factors that have not been extensively studied in previous studies. Specifically, we are dividing perceived value into two factors: financial value and environmental value. Additionally, knowledge is divided into two factors: environmental knowledge and knowledge about new energy vehicles. We will also be examining new factors such as infrastructure and policy support. This study will present a valuable opportunity to make informed decisions regarding transportation modes and the importation of new energy vehicles. By facilitating the transition towards new energy vehicles, we can benefit from examining and analyzing factors influencing consumers' purchase intentions of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) in emerging global markets but also contribute to the development of sustainable transportation in the entire emerging global markets.

Literature Review

Introduction to Purchase intention of New Energy Vehicles and global scenario

Some previous scholars have noted that as the Earth continues to experience record-breaking temperatures, science confirms that climate change is inevitable. Along with the power sector and manufacturing industry, road transport is responsible for a significant portion of fossil fuel consumption and carbon emissions that contribute to global warming. To mitigate the adverse effects of climate change, New Energy vehicles are being promoted as effective clean mobility solutions. In many developed economies, there is a rapid shift from internal combustion engine-based vehicles (ICEVs) to NEVs. Cities such as Copenhagen, Oslo, London, Paris, and Amsterdam have set deadlines to ban fossil-fuel-based vehicles from their roads in bold attempts to phase out ICEVs (or "de-ICEing" initiatives). Despite the unprecedented number of newly released NEV models, the pace of adoption and overall market share remains low. Excluding Japan, Asian countries have seen tremendous growth in population and economy over the past three decades, with the vast majority of projected increases in greenhouse gas emissions expected to come from this continent. By 2030, Asia's share of worldwide transport sector-related CO₂ emissions is expected to increase to 31% (Asian Development Bank, 2018). In recognition of the threats of climate change, many countries have committed to reducing CO₂ emissions, as ratified by the United Nations Climate Change Conference (UNFCCC) in 2016. However, many of the emission reduction targets set by Asian governments are ambiguous and unquantified. Most scholarly work on New Energy vehicle adoption has focused on developed Western nations, as they are the earlier adopters of NEVs. Developing countries, as laggards in New Energy private passenger vehicle adoption, are not well positioned for the mass market of NEVs due to charging infrastructure limitations, low-income levels, and relatively higher costs of full New Energy Vehicles compared to internal combustion engine-based vehicles (Hamzah & Tanwir, 2020). However, when we consider the current situation of NEV adoption, China has become the top exemplary country that uses New Energy Vehicles in Asia and the world. According to previous scholars, because of the positive characteristics of new energy vehicles in reducing energy consumption, carbon emissions, and pollution, the development of the new energy vehicle industry is highly valued by governments of various countries. Additionally, it is regarded as an important strategic initiative to compete for the high ground of the economy and technology and enhance comprehensive national power. Both fossil fuel deficit countries (South Korea, Japan, and Belgium) and large carbon-emitting countries (France, UK, and USA) have a strong focus on the development of new energy vehicles. Global sales of electric vehicles also rose from less than 10,000 units in 2010 to 774,000 in 2016.

China has been the world's largest producer and seller of motor vehicles for several years and is also the largest emitter of greenhouse gases, making motor vehicle pollution sources an important source of air pollution. Several

serious air pollution incidents have aroused environmental awareness, and New Energy Vehicles are one of the effective measures to control air pollution. To achieve the goals of peaking CO₂ emissions by 2030, reaching a share of around 20 percent in non-fossil energy consumption, and achieving carbon neutrality by 2060, China has also adopted a series of measures to promote the development of new energy vehicles, such as tax credits, pilot city construction, and transport planning. At the same time, the government's proposal to encourage the use of new energy vehicles is of great significance in the context of building a beautiful China and reconceptualizing the harmonious coexistence between man and nature. In the New Energy Vehicle Industry Development Plan promulgated in September 2013, it was proposed that the target of 5 million new energy vehicles production and sales should be achieved by 2020. However, public acceptance of new energy vehicles is generally low, especially in the less developed areas of Western China. Due to inadequate supporting facilities and low public awareness of new energy vehicles, among other reasons, the public is taking a wait-and-see attitude, resulting in a smaller market share for new energy vehicles (Wang et al., 2021).

Previous scholars have mentioned that new energy technologies have the potential to increase productivity and improve the quality of life under conditions of poverty and deprivation. They also have the potential to bring greater changes to societies that are not accustomed to continuous technological change. The impact of new technologies on the public in developing countries is greater than in industrialized countries. Therefore, more attention needs to be paid to the acceptance of new energy vehicles in less developed countries and regions. However, research on the acceptance of new energy vehicles is mostly concentrated in industrialized countries and economically developed cities, while research in developing countries and regions is relatively rare (Wang et al., 2021). However, despite potential benefits that NEVs offer like the low maintenance or running costs, zero emissions, absence of air and noise pollution and driving pleasure, the demand for this technology has not shot up in the Indian market (Arora et al., 2022). Further, the studies that focused on vehicles are almost related to hybrid vehicles and a careful study of the literature reveals that the green purchase towards the electrical vehicle has not been thoroughly investigated. Therefore, a clear understanding of factors that influence consumer green purchase intention towards electrical vehicle is very essential at present. This created a need for further studies about green buyer behavior to be conducted in those developing countries (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021).

Theoretical Foundation

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action and is commonly used to study behavioral intention and behavior. It states that behavior is influenced by behavioral intention, which is determined by attitude towards the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control. Recently, scholars have used the TPB model to study environmentally friendly behavior, such as consumers' intention to recycle waste and adolescents' intentions to commute by car or bicycle. The model has been found to be a valuable framework for explaining these intentions, as various psychological determinants, including attitudes and norms, have a significant impact on the intention to engage in environmentally friendly behavior (Wang et al., 2014).

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is an extension of the Theory of Reasoned Action that considers both internal and external factors in influencing a person's behavioral intention. According to TPB, individual behaviors are influenced by their behavioral intention, which is in turn affected by their "subjective norm" and "attitude". Previous studies have shown that TPB can be used to measure environmentally friendly behavior. Additionally, TPB has been widely used in transport research to predict behavioral intention (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021).

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was proposed by Davis in 1989 as an extension of the Theory of Rational Action (TRA). The TRA was originally used to explain and predict people's willingness and behavior in accepting new technologies. Davis emphasized that personal acceptance of information technology is primarily influenced by factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and attitudes towards technology. Perceived usefulness refers to how individuals perceive a new technology to be more productive, while perceived ease of use refers to the effort required when using a new technology. Additionally, there is a relationship between these two factors, as perceived ease of use indirectly affects willingness to use by influencing perceived usefulness.

The TAM model provides a theoretical framework for the study of new technologies, such as smart homes and internet technologies, and has become one of the most influential research models for the acceptance and use of new technologies by individuals. The theoretical basis of TAM is highly universal, making it applicable to a wide range of technologies. Its scope has been continuously expanded in practical applications, with scholars using the TAM model to study individual biological control strategies, biogas, liquefied natural gas, electric vehicles, and more. This demonstrates that TAM can also be used to study people's intention to use clean energy or new energy vehicles (Wang et al., 2021).

Factors Impacting Purchase Intention for New Energy Vehicles

Related to the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Technology Acceptance Model, we examine factors influencing the purchase intention of NEVs in emerging global markets. This section will review literature related to purchase intention, social influence, attitude, environmental knowledge, New Energy Vehicle knowledge, perceived value, perceived environmental value, perceived financial value, policy support, and infrastructure maturity.

Purchase intention

Purchase intention is the consumer's willingness to buy a particular product or service (Xie et al., 2021; Arora et al., 2022). It represents the likelihood of an individual being ready to purchase a specific product in the near future (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021). The stronger the purchase intention, the more likely the consumer is to make the purchase. It is considered the best predictor of purchase behavior. Purchase intention is influenced by factors such as attitudes towards the product, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, price perception, perceived quality of the product, and environmental knowledge in the context of green consumerism. It plays a significant role in spreading NEV (New Energy Vehicle) brands among potential customers and improving the manufacturing sector (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2021). Due to its importance, scholars have done a lot of research to investigate the factors that influence the purchase intention of consumers. It is often influenced by factors such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitudes towards the product or technology, subjective norms, perceived risks, supportive policies, costs, price perception, and perceived quality of the product. In the context of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), purchase intention plays a significant role in spreading NEV brands among potential customers and improving the manufacturing sector (Suhud & Willson, 2019; Wang et al., 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Shi & Cheng, 2023). The factors that influence purchase intention include attitudes towards the product or technology, subjective norms, perceived risks, supportive policies, costs, price perception, perceived quality of the product, consumer's knowledge of product features and attributes, perceived control over financial capability, environmental knowledge, and perceived value of environmentally friendly products within the realm of green consumerism (Suhud & Willson, 2019; Wang et al., 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Shi & Cheng, 2023). Green purchase intention can be defined as the likelihood of a consumer to buy environmentally friendly products instead of non-eco-friendly products when considering a purchase. In the context of green consumerism, purchase intention can be influenced by environmental knowledge and the perceived value of environmentally friendly products (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021). Green products refer to goods that have a lesser impact on the environment compared to

traditional products. In the context provided, plug-in electric vehicles (PEVs), including battery electric vehicles (BEVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEV), are considered green products (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022). Purchase intention is vital as it is the most accurate predictor of purchasing behavior. It indicates the probability of a consumer buying a specific product or service and impacts their decision-making process. Furthermore, purchase intention significantly contributes to the dissemination of NEV (New Energy Vehicle) brands among potential customers and the enhancement of the manufacturing sector. Hence, comprehending and influencing purchase intention is essential for businesses and industries to efficiently target and engage potential customers.

External/ Social Influence

Social influence can be defined as a state where someone complies with the expectations of another or considers the information acquired from another as a sign of reality. It occurs when people alter their thoughts, beliefs, behaviors in accordance to their society and surroundings. Individuals get social influence from various sources such as friends, family, educators, employers, professional colleagues, experts, media, associates, salespeople and even strangers. It refers to the external social pressure that individuals perceive when performing a specific behavior, including the behavioral decisions and opinions of relatives, friends, and neighbors. It is a key factor in behavioral studies and can significantly impact purchase intentions and behaviors (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022; Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Suhud & Willson, 2019).

Social influence is important as it significantly impacts individuals' thoughts, beliefs, and behaviors, making them comply with societal expectations. It is a key factor in behavioral studies and plays a vital role in people's engagement with innovative products. Social influence can come from various sources such as friends, family, educators, employers, colleagues, media, and even strangers (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022; Lakshika & Hemamali). It can affect purchase intentions and behaviors, particularly in the adoption of new technologies or products. It is also seen in the adoption of environmentally friendly practices like the use of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs).

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and social influence are closely related. Social influence refers to the impact that one's social network can have on their behaviors and decisions. It is a key factor in behavioral studies and can significantly change a person's purchase intention. This is particularly evident in the adoption of new technologies like New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), where people tend to adopt these vehicles when they see others in their social network doing so. Social influence can come from various sources such as friends, family, coworkers, media, and even strangers (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021; Suhud & Willson, 2019).

According to past researchers, social influence is one of the key factors for the spread of NEVs in the market. The purchase intention of a person will change significantly according to social influence. Previous researchers have mentioned that peers, coworkers, colleagues, friends, family members, and role models are very important in influencing a buyer's choice (Xie et al., 2021). Especially when it comes to a very new product, it is very normal to seek the experience or the idea from a trustworthy, loved, respectable, known, or responsible person (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022). As mentioned earlier, social influence plays a vital role in people's engagement with innovative products like NEVs. Therefore, social influence is one of the key factors for NEV purchase intention.

Attitude

Attitude refers to the lasting positive or negative emotions towards a person, object, or issue. It affects behavior, including the intention to make a purchase, and can be shaped by observation, experience, and research. It represents a person's assessment of a specific behavior and their emotions towards an object or idea, serving as a connection between opinions and actions (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2021). In the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), attitude refers to the personal acceptance of information technology, influenced by factors such as perceived usefulness and ease of use. It is a psychological factor that directly affects

consumers' acceptance of innovative products and services. If the public believes that a certain technology is useful, they are more likely to hold a positive attitude that induces willingness to accept it. Attitude is a key factor in predicting one's behavior, including purchase intention (Wang et al., 2021). According to past studies, Attitude plays a major role in spreading NEV brands among potential customers and improving the manufacturing sector (Shi & Cheng, 2023).

Attitude is important as it refers to individuals' positive or negative evaluations regarding certain behavior, products, or services. It is a leading factor in measuring individuals' intentions or preferences and is a key predictor of one's behavior, including purchase intentions. Attitude also acts as a link between the opinions or thoughts an individual has and their ultimate behavior (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021) in the context of technology or environmental issues, a positive attitude can lead to acceptance of innovative products and services, or the promotion of environmental protection. In markets such as the New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), attitude can directly affect product purchasing behavior and influence strategic decisions. A positive shift in attitude can lead to market growth and attract potential customers

Attitude towards NEVs (New Energy Vehicles) refers to how consumers perceive or feel about these vehicles. This perception can greatly impact their likelihood of purchasing NEVs. Attitude acts as a link between the opinions or thoughts an individual has and their ultimate behavior, such as the decision to purchase. If people have a positive attitude towards NEVs, they are more willing to consider purchasing them. This shift in attitude is crucial for the growth of the NEV market (Shi & Cheng, 2023). However; some individuals still have traditional attitudes and negative perceptions about NEVs, often favoring conventional fuel-driven vehicle brands (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022).

Attitude is a key factor for the NEV market. People still have some traditional attitudes and negative perceptions about NEVs. Some individuals are biased towards conventional fuel-driven vehicle brands due to reasons such as social status, ego, pride, or lack of knowledge (Shi & Cheng, 2023). Previous studies have shown that if people have a positive attitude towards NEVs, they are more willing to change their mindset and consider purchasing NEVs. This shift in attitude will be crucial for the growth of the NEV market and for attracting potential customers who currently own conventional vehicles.

Environmental Knowledge

Environmental knowledge refers to the understanding and awareness of facts, concepts, and relationships concerning the natural environment and its ecosystems. This includes knowledge about the impacts of human activities on the environment, renewable energies, environmentally friendly products, and environmental policies. It can influence people's behaviors and decisions, such as their willingness to purchase and use green products, and the adoption of eco-friendly practices (Xie et al., 2021; Suhud & Willson, 2019; Shi & Cheng, 2023; Nimi, 2020; Wang et al., 2021; Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022).

Environmental knowledge has several benefits. It can influence people's attitudes, behaviors, and decisions related to environmental protection, such as the adoption of eco-friendly products or practices (Shi & Cheng, 2023). It can also increase the willingness to buy green products and is a key driving factor in green consumer behavior (Suhud & Willson, 2019). Furthermore, it can enhance understanding and awareness about the environment and how various factors, actions, and products can impact it. This includes knowledge about renewable energies, the benefits of environmentally friendly products, and the impacts of environmental pollution on public health (Wang et al., 2021). It also involves understanding the importance of implementing effective emission reduction policies and the role of renewable energy and sustainable practices in mitigating environmental damage (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022).

Environmental knowledge is an important factor for the purchase intention of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs). As people become more informed about the environment and the benefits of low-carbon preferences and NEVs, their willingness to purchase such vehicles increases (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021). This knowledge can influence people's

behaviors and decisions, making them more likely to choose environmentally friendly products like NEVs. It is seen as a key driving factor in green consumer behavior (Arora et al., 2022).

According to past studies, environmental knowledge is a key factor in motivating people to switch from conventional vehicles to NEVs. As people become more informed about the environment, their knowledge about NEVs also expands. With a broader understanding of environmental issues, people tend to become more environmentally friendly citizens. Many people believe that purchasing an NEV is a responsible choice to address global environmental problems and to demonstrate their commitment as responsible global citizens.

Knowledge about New Energy Vehicles

Knowledge about New Energy Vehicles refers to the understanding and information about New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), which are vehicles that use alternative, sustainable forms of energy instead of conventional gasoline. This includes knowledge about their eco-friendly characteristics, performance, technology, industry, and policies related to NEVs, as well as the infrastructure needed for these vehicles. It also involves understanding the negative impact of traditional vehicle consumption on the environment, the role of government and policymakers in promoting NEVs, and the challenges and limitations of NEVs. This knowledge significantly impacts the public acceptance of NEVs and the intention to make environmentally friendly, green products purchases (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022 and Suhud & Willson, 2019).

The benefits of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) include their utilization of green technology, optimized driving efficiency compared to conventional vehicles, and a positive effect on the environment. They have the potential to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, contribute to environmental protection, and decrease dependence on foreign oil (Arora et al., 2022). NEVs are also more affordable and environmentally friendly, contributing to reducing air pollution. They are cost-effective compared to traditional vehicles. Additionally, NEVs can create new business opportunities and are being promoted by various incentives and strategies.

New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) include electric vehicles, plug-in hybrid electric vehicles, fuel cell vehicles, solar-powered and hydrogen-based fuel-cell cars. Low-Cost Green Cars (LCGCs) are also a category of NEVs (Suhud & Willson, 2019) that are more affordable and environmentally friendly. They use alternative, sustainable forms of energy instead of traditional petrol. NEVs are seen as a promising strategy to reduce air pollution and mitigate climate change as they produce fewer greenhouse gas emissions and air pollution than vehicles that consume fossil fuel. However, the NEV industry is characterized by immature technology, high research and development risk, and uncertainty. NEVs also require technological breakthroughs and sufficient charging infrastructure. Governments of many countries have strategic plans for the development of the NEV industry, including implementing subsidy policies to promote the use of NEVs (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022).

According to past studies, knowledge about NEVs plays a vital role in the adoption of NEVs among customers. Due to a lack of knowledge and a tendency to fear new innovative technologies (Wang et al., 2021), there are many negative messages spread in society about NEVs. Even some traditional engineers and technical people do not recommend new technological vehicles due to their insufficient knowledge or reliance on outdated information. By spreading real positive factors about NEVs through mass media or new media (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022), the NEV industry can raise awareness among the public. With NEV knowledge, people will be more inclined to choose a NEV as their new vehicle.

Perceived Value

Perceived value refers to the worth or value that a product or service has in the mind of the consumer. It's the customer's evaluation of the merits of a product or service, and its ability to meet their needs and expectations, especially in comparison to its peers. This perception directly influences their acceptance and usage of the product or

service. It can be influenced by various factors such as the product's environmental impact, the availability of infrastructure supporting its use, and the risks associated with new technologies (Shi & Cheng, 2023; Nimi, 2020; Arora et al., 2022; Suhud & Willson, 2019; Meckler-Pacheco, 2022).

Perceived value is important because it directly influences a consumer's purchase intention and usage of a product or service. It is the worth or value that a product or service has in the mind of the consumer, based on their assessment of its usefulness, cost, and risk (Nimi, 2020). This perception can be influenced by various factors such as the product's environmental impact, brand name, and the availability of supporting infrastructure. A positive perceived value can lead to a positive attitude towards the product and a higher likelihood of purchase.

Perceived value refers to the benefits and advantages that consumers believe a product or service holds for them. In the context of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), perceived value can be influenced by factors such as the product's environmental impact, the availability of infrastructure supporting its use, and the risks associated with new technologies. Positive perceived values of NEVs include environmental benefits, less noise, instant acceleration, a smooth driving experience, and less costly fuel. Negative perceived values include functional barriers such as limited distance, long waiting times for charging, scarce charging stations, and fear of being stranded. Improving infrastructure, promoting environmental benefits, and consumers' willingness to embrace new technologies can increase the perceived value of NEVs.

The perceived value of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) can be increased by improving the infrastructure supporting their use, such as charging stations, and promoting their environmental benefits. Reducing the risks associated with new technologies and providing positive pre-purchase experiences can also enhance their perceived value. Additionally, addressing functional barriers like limited distance, long charging times, and fear of being stranded can improve the perceived value (Arora et al., 2022). Lastly, educating consumers about the benefits of NEVs, such as less environmental harm, less noise, instant acceleration, a smooth driving experience, and less costly fuel, can also increase their perceived value (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022).

When considering past research, it is evident that perceived value can vary according to a person's perspective about the product and the brand. However, the purpose of the product and the psychological value that the buyer assigns to it will be key factors in identifying the perceived value (Wang et al., 2021; Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021). The same product with the same purpose may be priced differently according to the brand name due to the demands of buyers. This is what we can identify as the perceived value. In bargain shops, we can see that some products have a very high demand and price, even if they are not valuable material-wise. On the other hand, some products have less demand even though they have high material value. Perceived value can be considered a key factor in the purchase intention of an NEV.

Perceived Environmental Value

Perceived Environmental Value, also known as Green Consumption Value, refers to the tendency to value environmental protection through one's purchases and consumption behaviors. It involves showcasing environmental protection through behavior and placing importance on practices and products that are beneficial to the environment. This value makes people aware of their negative impact on the environment and aids them in selecting more environmentally friendly products in their purchase consideration. It can influence consumer attitudes and behaviors, including the decision to purchase environmentally friendly products like New Energy Vehicles (NEVs). Factors influencing perceived environmental value include green trust, green perceived quality, green perceived risk, environmental consciousness, and environmental knowledge (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021; Wang et al., 2021; Yeğin & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022; Suhud & Willson, 2019).

Environmental knowledge plays a significant role in influencing green purchase intentions. Individuals with a high environmental concern (EC) are more likely to adopt green products like New Energy Vehicles (NEVs). Additionally,

positive experiences with eco-innovation, products with green values, and environmental consciousness can strengthen the perceived environmental value and promote environmentally friendly actions. Therefore, having environmental knowledge can lead to a greater likelihood of considering and purchasing environmentally friendly products.

Perceived Environmental Value influences the purchase intention of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) in several ways. Individuals who perceive NEVs as environmentally friendly and of high quality are more likely to have a positive attitude towards purchasing them. Factors such as positive experiences with eco-innovation, products with green values, and environmental consciousness can strengthen this perceived value and promote environmentally friendly actions (Shi & Cheng, 2023). However, perceived functional barriers such as limited distance, long charging times, and scarce charging stations can negatively impact this value (Arora et al., 2022). Additionally, factors like price, maintenance cost, driving range, and charging infrastructure of NEVs can also influence the perceived environmental value and acceptance of such products. Therefore, the perceived environmental value can significantly impact the decision to purchase NEVs (Suhud & Willson, 2019). The impact of government subsidies on the environmental benefits of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) is seen as effective in improving urban air quality.

Perceived Environmental Value can improve through various factors and influences. These include positive experiences with eco-innovation, products with green values, and environmental consciousness, which can strengthen the perceived value and promote environmentally friendly actions. Additionally, factors such as green trust, green perceived quality, and green perceived risk can influence the improvement of perceived environmental value (Lakshika & Hemamali, 2021). Furthermore, increasing environmental awareness and measures to control urban air pollution, as well as government subsidies for environmentally friendly products like New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), can contribute to the improvement of perceived environmental value.

According to past researchers, we can identify perceived environmental value as a crucial factor for a person to decide to buy or use an environmentally friendly product. If the buyer or user has environmental knowledge, it will help us to identify the perceived environmental value. In the world, there are many green products that support the environmental protection process. Perceived environmental value creates a clear picture for the customer about the products' environmentally friendly features and their contribution to the protection of the environment by reducing carbon dioxide emissions. It also helps customers compare and identify the environmental damage caused by conventional fuel vehicles and the best environmental protection value of NEVs. This analysis can be more in-depth compared to traditional customers and environmentally conscious customers as Green Citizens.

Perceived Financial value

Perceived financial value refers to the consumer's evaluation of the monetary worth of a product or service. It is influenced by factors such as price, quality, brand image, and the individual's overall financial situation. This perception plays a significant role in influencing purchase intentions. In the context of new technologies like New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), perceived financial value can be enhanced by government measures like vehicle carbon tax, special roads for NEVs, and congestion pricing. It can also be measured using various indexes such as return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE), return on investment (ROI), and profit (Wang et al., 2021). It can also refer to the individual's assessment of the financial benefits and costs associated with a particular policy or action (Wang et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2021; Nimi, 2020; Shi & Cheng, 2023; Suhud & Willson, 2019).

The benefits of perceived financial value include influencing consumers' purchase decisions and intentions. It can make certain products or services, such as New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) and green products, more attractive to consumers. It can also influence the perception of price, with higher prices sometimes being associated with better value for money. Furthermore, perceived financial value can reflect the financial performance of a company, as

measured by indexes like return on asset (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and return on investment (ROI) (Wang et al., 2021).

Knowing the financial value for the NEVs purchase intention is important because it influences the consumer's decision to buy. It includes the consumer's evaluation of the monetary worth of the vehicle, the cost of charging versus traditional fuel, potential savings from environmental benefits, and possible financial incentives like tax benefits. Perceived financial value can also impact the consumer's perception of the product's quality, brand image, and their overall financial situation (Wang et al., 2021; Arora et al., 2022). It can also affect the consumer's perception of the product's performance, safety, fuel efficiency, and overall environmental benefits. Therefore, understanding the perceived financial value can significantly impact the intention to purchase NEVs.

The financial benefits of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) include long-term financial gains for the buyers, potentially due to factors like performance, safety, fuel efficiency, and overall environmental benefits. NEVs may also come with financial incentives such as various tax benefits (Shi & Cheng, 2023). However, these benefits can be influenced by factors like the scale of subsidies, market response, and government policies.

The financial or fiscal value will be the value of the product. As a buyer, perceived financial value is very crucial for making a decision related to high-value expenditures like buying a vehicle. It is like a lifetime decision, one of the main decisions of a person's life. The benefits of conventional vehicles and NEVs can be measured by the perceived financial value. According to past researchers mentioned in NEVs, they will cause to gain long-term financial benefits for the buyers. Maybe due to the initial cost factor, people do not purchase NEVs, but if they deeply consider the measurement of the perceived financial value of the product in the longer term, they will choose to go for the NEV. Perceived financial value can be identified as an important factor for the purchase intention of NEVs.

Policy Support

Policy support refers to the measures taken by the government or other institutions to promote or facilitate certain activities or industries. This can include subsidies, incentives, regulations, and other forms of assistance. Examples from the context include promoting the adoption of new energy vehicles through direct purchase subsidies, purchase tax exemptions, free parking, no traffic restrictions, and expanding the network of electric charging stations (Wang et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2021; Arora et al., 2022; Shi & Cheng, 2023; Meckler-Pacheco, 2022).

Policy support for New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) is important as it encourages the adoption and growth of the NEV industry (Arora et al., 2022). This can be achieved through measures such as tax reductions, free number plates, purchase subsidies, support for building NEV infrastructure, simple regulations, low-cost insurance policies, and renewable permits. Policy support can also help address environmental problems by promoting green products like NEVs (Wang et al., 2021). Furthermore, it can increase public acceptance of NEVs by reducing their perceived cost and addressing concerns about their use (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022).

The future of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) looks promising with strong policy backing. Measures such as tax reduction, free number plates, subsidies for purchasing NEVs, support for building NEV infrastructure with loans, and simple regulations can help to stimulate the growth of the NEV industry (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022). Additionally, efforts to promote the use of NEVs through allowing charging vendors to operate without a license, reducing taxes, and building a network of recharging stations are also beneficial. Other strategies include low-cost insurance policies, annual low-cost renewable permits, and reduced custom fees for importing NEVs.

Past studies have shown that government policy support is one of the key factors for the growth of an industry, especially when it comes to innovative or environmentally sensitive products. It is essential to have strong policy backing for the proliferation of such products in society, particularly when there are established players in the market. When it comes to environmentally friendly products, it is crucial to have government support or support from other responsible bodies. Environmental problems need to be addressed by promoting green products (Wang et al., 2021).

Government policies such as tax reduction, free number plates for NEVs, subsidies for purchasing NEVs, support for building NEV infrastructure with loans, and simple regulations can help to kick start the NEV industry in the country. Furthermore, implementing simple regulations for the growth or establishment of the NEV industry is crucial (Xie et al., 2021). Other measures such as low-cost insurance policies, annual low-cost renewable permits, permits for purchasing NEVs, and reduced custom fees for importing NEVs can also encourage the growth of the NEV industry. Furthermore, increasing conventional vehicle taxes and introducing new taxes on related products can also contribute to increasing the purchase intention of NEVs.

Infrastructure Maturity

Infrastructure maturity refers to the development and availability of necessary facilities and systems for a particular service or product. In the context of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs), infrastructure maturity specifically refers to the development of charging infrastructure for NEVs, including charging stations and other related facilities. It encompasses factors such as technological maturity, standards, research funds, support policies, and public acceptance, all of which greatly impact the sustainable development of NEVs. The maturity of infrastructure is crucial for establishing trust among buyers and encouraging the adoption of NEVs (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022; Arora et al., 2022; Shi & Cheng, 2023; Wang et al., 2021).

The importance of infrastructure maturity lies in its impact on the sustainable development and public acceptance of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) and other relevant technologies. Specifically, in the context of NEVs, infrastructure maturity, which includes the development of charging infrastructure, technological standards, research funds, support policies, and public acceptance, greatly influences the adoption and trust in NEVs (Wang et al., 2021). Additionally, infrastructure maturity is crucial for encouraging the transition to new technologies, reducing carbon emissions, mitigating climate change, and improving air quality through the development of urban transportation systems and other environmental protection measures. Overall, infrastructure maturity plays a vital role in shaping consumer behavior, industry growth, and environmental sustainability.

Customers are significantly impacted by infrastructure maturity, especially in the context of New Energy Vehicles (NEVs). The availability and accessibility of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles greatly influence customers' decisions to purchase NEVs (Arora et al., 2022). Robust charging infrastructure is essential for addressing customers' concerns about range anxiety and ensuring that they can conveniently recharge their vehicles. Additionally, infrastructure maturity affects customers' trust and confidence in NEVs, as well as their overall acceptance of new technologies.

Furthermore, infrastructure maturity can also impact customers living in low-income and rural communities, as well as those residing in housing types that do not allow for accessible at-home charging. In these cases, the lack of infrastructure may deter customers from purchasing NEVs, highlighting the importance of infrastructure development in addressing diverse customer needs and encouraging widespread adoption of NEVs (Shi & Cheng, 2023).

Several countries prioritize the development of infrastructure for NEVs. Some of the leading countries in this regard include China, Norway, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. These nations have implemented various initiatives and incentives to support the growth of NEV infrastructure, such as building charging stations, offering subsidies for electric vehicle purchases, and implementing policies to reduce emissions from traditional vehicles (Shi & Cheng, 2023)

The NEV industry is still growing. NEVs are mainly powered by electric power, batteries, hydrogen, or solar energy. Electric vehicles are particularly popular among users. However, these vehicles need to be powered with energy (Meckler-Pacheco, 2022).

NEVs can be recharged at rechargeable centers, battery swapping stations, hydrogen stations, or solar power panel centers. However, the world still has major facilities for conventional fuel vehicles, such as petrol, diesel, or gas stations. Countries like China, the USA, and Europe have undertaken mega construction projects to develop infrastructure related to NEVs in their countries. However, other regional countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America need to become more familiar with the NEV industry (Yeğın & Ikram, 2022). When it comes to NEV infrastructure, maturity is important for establishing trust among buyers. China, the USA, and some European countries that have worked on developing NEV-related infrastructure have now become very mature. However, other countries are still in the early or developing stages. The future of NEVs hinges on the continued progress of infrastructure maturity, which is essential for building trust among buyers, promoting widespread adoption, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of NEVs as a viable transportation option. According to past studies, infrastructure maturity is a significant factor in the purchase intention of NEVs.

Further studies areas

This article provides a robust foundation for further studies on Factors influencing the purchase intention of NEVs in emerging global markets. Several avenues for future research emerge from the analysis presented:

- **Quantitative Studies:** The article primarily focuses on a conceptual framework and literature review. If a researcher is interested in conducting quantitative studies using surveys and statistical analysis, they could empirically test the relationships between the identified factors and purchase intention. This article would provide stronger evidence for the suggested models and allow for more precise predictions of consumer behavior.
- **Cross-Cultural Comparisons:** The article acknowledges the importance of emerging markets but focuses on a general framework. Comparative studies across different emerging markets, considering cultural nuances, economic conditions, and infrastructure development levels, would provide valuable insights into the specific factors driving NEV adoption in each region.
- **Longitudinal Studies:** The article focuses on a snapshot of factors influencing purchase intention. Longitudinal studies tracking consumer behavior over time would be crucial to understand how factors like policy changes, technological advancements, and evolving social norms impact NEV adoption in the long term.
- **Focus on Specific Barriers:** The article identifies several barriers to NEV adoption, such as range anxiety, charging infrastructure limitations, and high initial cost. Further research could delve deeper into these specific barriers, exploring potential solutions and strategies to overcome them.
- **Integration of Behavioral Economics:** The article draws on established theories like TPB and TAM. Integrating concepts from behavioral economics, such as framing effects, loss aversion, and social norms, could provide a more nuanced understanding of consumer decision-making and offer insights into effective marketing and policy interventions.

By pursuing these research directions, we can gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complex factors influencing NEV adoption in emerging global markets, ultimately contributing to the development of effective strategies for promoting sustainable transportation.

Conclusion

The transition to sustainable transportation is a critical step towards achieving global environmental goals. New Energy Vehicles (NEVs) offer a promising solution, but their widespread adoption hinges on understanding and addressing the factors influencing consumer purchase intentions in emerging global markets. This study, drawing

upon the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Technology Acceptance Model, highlights the multifaceted nature of this decision-making process.

This analysis reveals that environmental knowledge, NEV knowledge, external/social influence, attitude, policy support, and infrastructure maturity are key drivers of purchase intention. Consumers with a strong understanding of environmental issues and the benefits of NEVs are more likely to consider them. Social influence, particularly from trusted sources, plays a significant role in shaping perceptions and encouraging adoption. Positive attitudes towards NEVs, fostered by awareness of their environmental and financial benefits, are essential for overcoming traditional biases.

Furthermore, perceived value factors, including financial value and environmental value, significantly impact purchase intention. Consumers are more likely to embrace NEVs when they perceive them as financially viable, offering long-term cost savings and potential incentives. A strong perceived environmental value, driven by a sense of responsibility and a desire to contribute to a sustainable future, further motivates purchase.

Policy support is crucial for accelerating the transition to NEVs. Governments can play a vital role by implementing incentives, such as subsidies, tax breaks, and infrastructure development, to reduce the perceived cost and risk associated with NEVs. Infrastructure maturity, particularly the availability of charging stations and other supporting facilities, is essential for building consumer confidence and addressing range anxiety.

This study underscores the importance of a holistic approach to promoting NEV adoption in emerging global markets. By addressing the interconnected factors influencing purchase intention, policymakers and industry stakeholders can develop effective strategies to accelerate the transition to sustainable transportation. This includes fostering environmental awareness, promoting NEV knowledge, leveraging social influence, cultivating positive attitudes, providing robust policy support, and investing in infrastructure development. By working together, we can create a future where NEVs become the preferred mode of transportation, contributing to a cleaner, healthier, and more sustainable world.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Wang, R., Zhao, X., Wang, W. and Jiang, L. (2021). 'What factors affect the public acceptance of new energy vehicles in underdeveloped regions? A case study of Gansu Province, China,' *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 318, p. 128432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128432>. [Accessed: 04 September 2023].
- [2] Yeğın, T. and Ikram, M. (2022) Analysis of consumers' electric vehicle purchase intentions: An expansion of the theory of planned behavior, MDPI. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912091> [Accessed: 04 November 2023].
- [3] Arora, S.C., Sharma, M. and Singh, V.K. (2022) Using diffusion of Innovation Framework with attitudinal factor to predict the future of mobility in the Indian market - environmental science and Pollution Research, Using diffusion of innovation framework with attitudinal factor to predict the future of mobility in the Indian market | Environmental

Science and Pollution Research. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11356-022-23149-8> [Accessed: 04 September 2023].

[4] Lakshika, V.G.P. and Hemamali, K.A.G.A. (2021) *Antecedents of the green purchase intention towards electric cars: the sri lankan customers' perspective*, (PDF) *antecedents of the green purchase intention ... - researchgate*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/350808652_Antecedents_of_the_green_purchase_intention_towards_electric_cars_the_Sri_Lankan_customers%27_perspective (Accessed: 11 September 2023).

[5] Hamzah, M.I. and Tanwir, N.S. (2021) 'Do pro-environmental factors lead to purchase intention of hybrid vehicles? The moderating effects of environmental knowledge,' *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 279, p. 123643. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123643>. [Accessed: 24 September 2023].

[6] Wang, S., Fan, J., Zhao, D., Yang, S. and Fu, Y. (2014) Predicting consumers' intention to adopt hybrid electric vehicles: Using an extended version of the theory of Planned Behavior Model - Transportation, SpringerLink. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11116-014-9567-9> (Accessed: 18 September 2023).

[7] Ahmed, A.A. and Gomah, M. (2023) Electric Vehicle Impact on the Sustainable Development Goals Considering Renewable Energy Sources Integration [Preprint].

[8] Meckler-Pacheco, A. (2022) *How Do Consumers Become Aware of Electric Vehicles? A Qualitative Approach* [Preprint].

[9] Shi, Z. and Cheng, J. (2023) How do government subsidies and consumers' low-carbon preference promote new energy vehicle diffusion? A tripartite evolutionary game based on energy vehicle manufacturers, the government and consumers, *Cell*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14327> [Accessed: 25 September 2023].

[10] Xie, Y., Wu, D. and Zhu, S. (2021) Can new energy vehicles subsidy curb the urban air pollution? Empirical evidence from pilot cities in China, *ScienceDirect*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.142232> [Accessed: 25 September 2023].

[11] Nimi, K.S. (2020) Environment value: concept and measurement, *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra2013> [Accessed: 25 September 2023].

[12] Usep Suhud;Greg Willson;*Low-Cost Green Car Purchase Intention: Measuring the Role of Brand Image on Perceived Price and Quality* (2019) iv,238-249

Mr. Hirantha Sandun Athulathmudali.

